

SHAPE MEMORY AND ELECTROMAGNETIC INTERFERENCE SHIELDING EFFECT OF CNT/SMP NANOCOMPOSITES

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Abstract

The nanocomposites with carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and shape memory polymer (SMP) were developed for mechanical and electrical applications. The specimens with different CNTs weight fractions were prepared. Their mechanical property, particularly for the shape memory behavior, and electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding effectiveness (SE) were investigated. As a result, for the developed nanocomposites, the mechanical strength and modulus increased obviously due to the filler of carbon nanotubes. Using carbon nanotubes, the shape memory effect of SMP bulk can be kept well and the recovery stress in the developed CNT/SMP nanocomposites is much larger than the SMP bulk. Raman spectra technique was used to evaluate nano-mechanical characterization on CNT and polymer interface and the reasonable relationship between Raman spectra shift and applied strains was observed. Furthermore, the experiments to evaluate EMI SE were carried out in three different frequency bands, 18~26.5 GHz (K band), 33~50 GHz (Q band) and 50~75 GHz (V band). The EMI SE of CNT/SMP nanocomposite had a strong dependence of CNT content and the specimen thickness at all of three frequency bands. The higher the frequency, the larger the EMI SE is.

1 Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are receiving steadily increasing attention because of their unique structural and electrical characteristics. The tensile modulus and strength of CNTs reach 270 GPa to 1 TPa and 11-200 GPa, respectively [1-2]. The unusual electrical and mechanical properties of carbon nanotubes have motivated a flurry of interests to exploit their applications in advanced

composite materials, particularly polymer based composites, to improve the performance of a matrix or to achieve new properties [3]. Recently, because various composition technologies were established and the cost of CNT decreased due to a large quantity production, the more and more applications for CNTs have been developed. Many researches on mechanical, thermal and electric characterizations of CNT reinforced polymers are reported, such as CNT/polystyrene [4,5], CNT/PVA [6], CNT/PVDF [7], CNT/PP [8-12], CNT/nylon [13], and CNT/epoxy [14-16] etc.

On the other hand, shape memory polymers (SMPs) have the characteristics such as large recoverability, lightweight, superior molding property and lower cost. These advantages have resulted in that the SMPs become one of functional materials with much attention from many fields [17-19]. For shape memory polymer (SMP) of polyurethane series, its glass transfer temperature (T_g) may be set up around the room temperature, and its characterizations such as shape recovery and/or shape fixation may appear to be quite different at the temperature above and below T_g [20-25]. Thus the polyurethane SMP is respected to have wide applications in the field of industry as an actuation material.

In this paper, SMP nanocomposites with carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are developed and their unique characteristics, such as shape memory effect, electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding effect [26-32] are investigated for the wider applications in mechanical and electrical/electronic fields.

2 Experimental Work

2.1 Materials

The carbon nanotubes of VGCFs provided from Showa Denko K.K. are used as fillers. The diameter

of VGCF is about 150 nm, and the length is 10~20 μm . The polyesterpolyol series of polyurethane shape memory polymer (SMP) is used as matrix and its glass transition temperature T_g is about 45°C . The raw material is liquid. The weight ratio of polymer to solvent was set to be 3:7. SEM micrographs (see Fig. 1) for CNT/SMP nanocomposite developed shows that VGCFs exhibit relatively good dispersion in SMP and are of 1~2 hundred nanometers in thickness and several microns in length. An interconnected conductive network has been formed in the materials.

Figure 1. Scanning electron micrograph of 5.0wt% VGCF/SMP nanocomposite.

Fig. 2. Three-dimensional stress-strain-temperature schematic in a thermo-mechanical cycle test;
 memorized shape after molding and cooling;
 free deformation due to the rubber elasticity of the amorphous portion by heating over T_g under an applied force;
 shape fixity by cooling below T_g ;
 shape recovery by heating over T_g under free load condition.

2.2 Thermo-mechanical cycle test

In order to investigate the shape recovery property of the developed nanocomposites, the thermo-mechanical cycle test was conducted (see Fig. 2). The specimen was pulled up to maximum strain ϵ_m at a constant tensile speed at the high temperature T_h above T_g (at the rubbery state) (Process 1). Maintaining the strain at ϵ_m , the specimen was cooled to the low temperature T_l below T_g (at the glassy state) and kept for 20 minutes (Process 2). The specimen was unloaded at the temperature T_l (Process 3), where small unloading strain ϵ_u occurred. Then the specimen was heated from T_l to T_h under no-load and kept for 5 minutes (Process 4), where the strain of the specimen was recovered. This is one completed thermo-mechanical cycle.

2.3 Recovery stress test

To measure the recovery stress, the specimen was kept for 10 minutes at low temperature T_l under no-load in the process 4, and then the test distance of the specimen was adjusted to have a constant strain. After that the specimen was heated from T_l to T_h and kept for 5 minutes at T_h under a constraint strain condition and the recovery stress was measured.

Fig. 3. The schematic of an EMI shielding effectiveness measurement system.

2.4 Electromagnetic interference (EMI) Shielding Effectiveness (SE)

For a millimeter wave band, the technique to evaluate EMI SE is known with two antennas arranged against. A specimen comparatively bigger than the opening area of a horn antenna is required for this evaluation because of the radiation pattern characteristic of a horn antenna. Here, the SE of VGCF/SMP nanocomposites is analyzed using a near-field antenna measurement system. The system illustration is shown in Fig. 3. EMI SE is defined by the difference of the transmitted powers between VGCF/SMP nanocomposite and the reference

specimen. For four developed VGCF/SMP nanocomposites and the SMP bulk as a reference specimen, their SE was measured in frequency ranges of 18~26.5GHz, 33~50GHz and 50~75GHz corresponding to K, Q and V band horn antenna and waveguide probe, respectively.

3 Result and Discussion

3.1 Shape memory property

The stress-strain curves obtained in the thermo-mechanical cycle test of the maximum strain $\varepsilon_m = 100\%$ for CNT/SMP nanocomposites and SMP bulk were shown in Fig. 4. Observing the same cycle number, when the VGCF weight fraction in CNT/SMP nanocomposites became high, the stress at the maximum strain became large, and the residual strain increased. The stress corresponding to any strain value during cycle loading also increased with the VGCF weight fraction, but the tendency of stress-strain curve on cycle number in CNT/SMP nanocomposites with 1.7, 3.3 and 5.0wt% of VGCFs weight fraction, respectively, is similar to that in SMP bulk. When cycle number increased the variation of stress-strain loop was large at an early stage, and it became small pronouncedly after cycle number $N=2$. The shape of stress-strain loop was almost the same after two cycles ($N>2$) although it moves to the higher strain side. The residual strain $\varepsilon_p(N)$ increased slowly accompanying with the reduction of recovery strain. This means that the addition of carbon nanotubes up to 5.0wt % weight fraction will not only make rise of the mechanical property but also almost keep the shape fixture property similar to the SMP bulk.

When the developed nanocomposites were cooled to the low temperature T_1 and kept for 20 minutes under the maximum strain ε_m (Process 2) stress in CNT/SMP nanocomposites decreased firstly due to stress relaxation and then increased due to heat contraction at T_1 during one cycle. The relationship between stress and time was shown in Fig.5 for the first typical cycle. The curves shifted to the high stress level with the increase of VGCF weigh fractions. The stress relaxation was large but thermal contraction stress was small in the cooling process of low temperature T_1 . Relaxation time became short with the increment VGCF weight fraction. However, the thermal stress became large due to heat contraction and relatively large Young's modulus at T_1 , so that the stress in Fig.5 increased obviously accompanying with the thermal contraction. The

stress increment became blunt and tended to constant after about 25 minutes.

Fig. 4. Stress-strain curves in the thermo-mechanical cycle tests at $\varepsilon_m = 100\%$ for (a) SMP bulk and (b) 3.3wt%.

Fig.5. Relationship between stress and time in the process 2 for four materials—SMP bulk, 1.7wt%, 3.3wt% and 5.0wt%.

The shape recovery property of CNT/SMP nanocomposites was examined from the result of thermo-mechanical cycle tests as above. The shape memory effect relative to both strain fixity and strain recovery were evaluated by using both strain fixity ratio and strain recovery ratio at cycle number N as defined by Eq.(1). The strain recovery ratio considering the residual strain per each cycle was used.

$$R_f(N) = \frac{\varepsilon_u(N) - \varepsilon_p(N-1)}{\varepsilon_m - \varepsilon_p(N-1)} \quad (1)$$

$$R_r(N) = \frac{\varepsilon_u(N) - \varepsilon_p(N)}{\varepsilon_u(N) - \varepsilon_p(N-1)}$$

Where $R_f(N)$ and $R_r(N)$ is the strain fixity ratio and the strain recovery ratio in the cycle number N , $\varepsilon_u(N)$ is the unloading strain in the process 3 at T_l in the cycle number N , $\varepsilon_p(N)$ and $\varepsilon_p(N-1)$ were residual strain in the cycle number N and $N-1$.

From equation (1), the relationship between the strain fixity ratio and the cycle number for the 3.3wt% specimen is shown in Fig. 6. The unloading strains almost took the fixed value near the maximum strain. The strain fixity ratio $R_f(N)$ for each specimen was about 95%. It is clear that the developed nanocomposites have good shape fixed property.

Fig. 6. Relationship between strain fixity ratio and cycle number for 3.3wt% nanocomposite.

The relationship between the strain recovery ratio and the cycle number is shown in Fig. 7. The strain recovery ratio after the second cycle is more than 90% and tended to be constant 95% after more cycle numbers. This phenomenon is called as a

training effect. For the developed nanocomposites with reinforcement of carbon nanotubes, stable strain recovery ability after several cycles of training could be obtained.

Fig. 7. Relationship between strain recovery ratio and cycle number.

3.2 Recovery stress

The stress-strain curves obtained in the recovery stress test for CNT/SMP nanocomposites and SMP bulk were shown in Fig. 8. The load curve and unload curve were similar to those in thermo-mechanical cycle tests. The specimens were kept for 10 minutes under stress free at low temperature T_l after unloading. It was observed in situ that the strain was recovered slowly during the keeping time. This recovered strain decreased with the increment of VGCF weight fraction. The recovered strain for 3.3wt% and 5.0wt% VGCF was almost the same. In order to measure the recovery stress for the application of actuator, such as temperature sensors etc., the strain was restrained by fix the specimen distance and then recovery stress was measured.

The relationship between the recovery stress and the VGCF fraction was shown in Fig. 9 and their typical values are listed in Table 1. It is clear that the recovery stress of CNT/SMP nanocomposites is larger than SMP bulk. Especially, for the nanocomposites of 3.3wt% VGCF weight fraction, the recovery stress increased about 2 times as large as that in SMP bulk. The reason for this result could be considered as that when a specimen was loaded under both constant strain and high temperature and then cooled to low temperature and unloaded, the carbon nanotubes may store elastic strain energy. When reheating the specimen, this stored elastic strain energy will release and CNT/SMP nanocomposites obtain larger recovery stress.

Fig. 8. Relationship between stress and strain in the recovery stress cycle test for (a) SMP bulk, and (b) 3.3wt% at $\epsilon_m = 50\%$.

Fig. 9. Relationships between recovery stress and VGCF weight fraction for CNT/SMP nanocomposites.

Table 1. Recovery strain at low temperature T_1

VGCF content	SMP bulk	1.7wt%	3.3wt%	5.0wt%
$\epsilon_m = 50\%$	10.3%	8.9	7.8	7.1
$\epsilon_m = 100\%$	16.6	8.9	7.1	7.3

3.3 EMI SE of VGCF/SMP nanocomposites

3.3.1 Time domain property

The electromagnetic wave through a shield material is measured and then far-field values are computed using a network analyzer. Then these values are converted by inverse Fourier transform, and the time dependence of the transmitted electromagnetic wave is obtained. The typical relationship between the time and transmitted electromagnetic waves is shown in Fig. 10 at V-band for the specimen with 3 mm thickness. The transmitted electromagnetic wave is observed within 0.6~0.8 ns for CNT/SMP nanocomposites and SMP bulk. When VGCFs weight fraction increases, the peak of transmitted electromagnetic wave decreased and shifted to right side (delay). This means that EMI SE will increase with the increment of VGCFs weight fraction. Since the transmitted electromagnetic waves were only broached by the time gating function in the network analyzer they should correspond to the transmitted energy. The transmitted electromagnetic waves reached after 0.8 ns were the diffracted ones detouring around the specimen.

Fig. 10 The time domain of the transmitted electromagnetic wave in the 3mm specimen.

3.3.2 Shielding effectiveness

The EMI SE of CNT/SMP nanocomposites for different bands at 3mm specimen is shown in Fig. 11. It is observed that EMI SE of CNT/SMP nanocomposites increased with VGCFs weight fraction at all frequency bands. The higher the frequency, the higher the value of EMI SE is. For the material of 6.7 wt% VGCFs, the value of EMI SE exceeded over 30 dB for any of three frequency bands, and its maximum value reached 65 dB. The value of EMI SE indicates how much incident signal

is blocked by the shielding medium. For the value of 10dB EMI SE, this means 90 % of incident signal is blocked, and for 20 dB, 99 % of incident signal is blocked. Many researches indicated that the reduction of signal strength by 30 dB would be adequate for 50 % cases in the applications of automotive and computer industries. And the reduction by 40 dB would fulfill 95 % of the requirements. It is clear that CNT/SMP nanocomposites are excellent shielding materials for electromagnetic interference, especially at high frequency.

Fig. 11. Shielding effectiveness in in different band frequency ranges for VGCF/SMP nanocomposites (3mm thickness).

4 Conclusions

In this paper, carbon nanotube-based shape memory polymer (SMP) nanocomposites were developed and their shape memory properties and EMI SE were examined. The results obtained are concluded as follows:

1. The developed nanocomposites have excellent shape recoverability. They can keep high strain recovery ability more than 90% after several cycles of training. This will lead that the developed materials can be utilized for the cycle use with any shape in daily life.

2. The recovery stress of CNT/SMP nanocomposites is much larger than SMP bulk. For the nanocomposite with 3.3wt% VGCF weight fraction, the recovery stress is about twice as large as that in SMP bulk. This characterization may be expected to the application of temperature sensor materials for CNT/SMP nanocomposites.

3. The EMI SE of CNT/SMP nanocomposites have a strong dependence of carbon nanotube content and the specimen thickness at all of three frequency bands. The higher frequency, the larger EMI SE is. The prediction for EMI SE is analyzed. For the materials with 5.5wt% VGCFs both experiment and analysis will agree well.

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